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Video Tutorial Designs for Learning: Facilitating Engagement and Entrepreneurship in Welfare, Learning and Experience Technology Engineering Students

L. B. Bertel

Postdoc

Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

E-mail: lykke@plan.aau.dk

G. Majgaard

Associate Professor

University of Southern Denmark

Odense, Denmark

E-mail: gum@mmpi.sdu.dk

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INTRODUCTION

This paper presents initial findings and first experiences with a problem-based learning approach to developing video tutorials with the aim of facilitating engagement and entrepreneurship in a course in Learning & Technology for 9th sem. students from Welfare Technology and Learning & Experience Technology, respectively.

Previously the course was offered only to students in Learning & Experience Technology (LET), however from 2017 going forward the course is offered to students from Welfare Technology as well. This proposes challenges related to increased diversity in theoretical knowledge, skills and competences related to learning theory and its application domains, differences in methodological approaches and practice as well as different expectations with regard to relevance to future careers. Furthermore, prior experiences with the course suggested a need to encourage a deeper understanding of the theories introduced on the course and a greater transferability of tools, methods and skills to other relevant contexts.

In an attempt to meet these challenges, the curriculum of the course in Learning and Technology was redesigned and a problem-based learning (PBL) approach [1] was implemented to facilitate engagement through active learning as well as the development of entrepreneurial engineering skills and competences through contextual application of theories and tools introduced in the course.

Central to the course was the students designing and developing a 5 min. instructional video related to a health/welfare technology or educational technology of their own choice. Since the students were all in their final year, many had developed prototypical technologies in prior projects applicable as cases in the course, whereas some chose technologies they would later be working on as part of their coming Master's thesis. Others are already employed part time either in their own company or one related to their profession, and chose a case relevant to said company.

The students worked in groups of three to four, and the mini-project consisted of three phases: (1) A design phase which included a problem analysis and 'user needs in context' studies. (2) A development phase in which the students were required to test their tutorials through two iterations and present their initial findings to each other at a status seminar. (3) An analytical and reporting phase in which the students reflected upon their tutorials, methods and results in relation to relevant learning theories and research methodologies. Throughout the course, sessions were offered on learning theories, user-centred design and evaluation methodologies as well as instructional sessions on tools for video tutorial design and development.

In the following, we will discuss the concept of designing video tutorials as a learning design, and relate it to relevant PBL principles. This is followed by a section describing our methodological approach and the type of data we collected as part of this case study. Finally, we will present our findings and reflections with the regard to learning outcomes and particularly in relation to facilitating student engagement and entrepreneurial engineering skills through video tutorial designs for learning.

1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this section, we will introduce and discuss research on video tutorials and their use in both formal and informal learning settings from both a consumer and producer perspective. Furthermore, we will elaborate on the PBL elements implemented in the curriculum design both generally and in relation to our particular focus on facilitating engagement and entrepreneurship in engineering students from Welfare Technology and Learning and Experience Technology.

1.1 Video Tutorials as Learning Designs

Video tutorials have long been replacing the paper tutorial [2], and an increasing use of educational video tutorials is seen in both formal and informal learning settings, ranging from video tutorials located by students themselves for study or leisure

purposes, to professional tutorial programs introduced by teachers as supplementary material or part of flipped curriculum initiatives [3]. When students use video tutorials on their own initiative, it is often a supplementary tool for understanding new and hard or particular hands-on topics like programming for which video tutorials are generally considered simple, rudimentary and authentic [4]. In flipped classroom or flipped curriculum initiatives, the video tutorial will often replace literature readings and general preparation [5].

The increasing availability of video tutorials enabled by open source platforms such as Youtube as well as easy access programs and tools for video production and editing is generally agreed to hold great potential when it comes to self-directed and student-centred learning [5]. However, only little research has been conducted on the learning potential of the design and making of these video tutorials as part of project and/or problem-based learning designs [4].

In [6] we found that the design of video tutorials held particular learning potential in relation to the application of theory in the design phase. This gave the students not only a language for articulated reflections on the user and context as well as aspects of the learning processes they were aiming to facilitate, but also a deeper understanding of the theory itself. Being both designers and consumers of video tutorials encouraged them to reflect upon design steps and decisions as well as the effect it has on the user and potential learning outcomes of watching these videos. Thus, to a certain degree the students evolved from native tutorial consumers to reflective tutorial designers [6].

On the other hand, the curriculum design also posed certain challenges related to the diversity of science cultures in different educational programmes as well as expectations toward applicability in future careers, which we will discuss and elaborate further in this paper.

1.2 Problem-Based Learning and Video Tutorials-based Learning Designs

Although video tutorials could generally be considered problem-oriented by definition, since they address a need for new knowledge and/or skills and often used upon encountering a particularly problem. However, the development of video tutorials is not necessarily problem-based, since the target audience and context is not always known or well described and thus the content is not necessarily situated and may cover more, less or something completely different from what is actually needed.

Thus, to further ensure a problem-oriented approach to the design and development of video tutorials in this course, we aimed to align the curriculum design with the following PBL learning principles (*Table 1*) common across different PBL models [7]:

Table 1. PBL learning principles

Approaches	Principles	Curriculum Design Decisions
Social (collaborative) learning approach	Teams	<i>The students worked in groups of 3-4 and collaborate in all phases of the project.</i>
	Participant-directed	<i>The students chose the case, generally opting for technologies they were already working with or had developed themselves</i>
Cognitive learning approach	Problem-based	<i>The students were required to do initial 'user needs in context'-studies to get a deeper understanding of the particular problem or need.</i>
	Project-oriented	<i>The task involved different complex problem analyses and implementation of problem-solving strategies within a given timeframe.</i>
	Experience	<i>The students were encouraged to draw from prior experiences with their chosen technologies and required to get new through user studies.</i>
	Context	<i>In addition to the 'UNICS' study, context was specifically addressed in lectures on research methodologies and evaluation.</i>
Content approach	Interdisciplinary	<i>The course covered two programmes (Welfare Technology and Learning & Experience Technology), however groups were not mixed</i>
	Exemplary	<i>Focus on translating theories and experience to other relevant contexts</i>
	Theory and practice including methodology	<i>Focus on translating theory to their coming professional practice and on developing a professional identity as a designer for learning</i>

2 METHODS AND DATA

Over the course of 13 weeks, the students were required to:

- Develop a 5 minute video tutorial and test with the target group in two iterations
- Develop a storyboard based on a 'user needs in context'-study
- Formulate learning objectives as part of the design process
- Hand in a 5 page report (with links to storyboards and two versions of the tutorial), discussing the design in relation to learning theory, research approach and methods as well as evaluation and results

The students designed and developed the tutorials using FlashBack Recorder, Camtasia Studio or similar to record screen, sound and webcam and tested these in two iterations with the target group. A status seminar was organized midway allowing the students to present preliminary work and provide each other feedback.

In addition to state of the art research on video tutorials as learning designs and an introduction to relevant tools, the curriculum included sessions on relevant user-centred research methodologies (action research, co-creation and design-based research); a session on interaction design and user behaviour (information architecture and persuasive technology, user needs in context, storyboarding); several sessions on learning theory (cognitivist and constructionist approaches to learning, tacit knowledge and learning processes and evolutionary learning models) as well as a session on evaluation design and strategies for implementation.

An internal wiki page was created on BlackBoard (see *figure 1*) for the students to upload and share problem statements, storyboards and design ideas, findings and reflections from tests as well as examples from their tutorials. The wiki-page allowed the students to get inspiration from and comment on each other's' work.

Figure 1. Examples of BlackBoard wiki pages

Empirical data for the evaluation of the teaching design included the developed tutorials and written assignments, wiki-pages, observations (from teaching and exams) and an open-ended questionnaire.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tutorial designs were very diverse and included both app- and website tutorials, e.g. explaining how to use an Augmented Reality museum app (*figure 2*) or tips and

tricks to ease and enhance the use of the local learning management system (*figure 3*) or explaining C++ programming in Visual Studio relevant to younger students at Welfare Technology (*figure 4*). Other tutorials introduced and explained the use of novel technology, either developed by the students themselves, e.g. a health device to improve back health in sedentary work situations (*figure 5*) or the programming of an educational robot (*figure 6*), or functioned as a prerequisite for using technology (in this case Hololens) for which the students had developed an application (*figure 7*).

Fig. 2. AR museum app tutorial

Fig. 3. BlackBoard tips&tricks tutorial

Fig. 4. C++ programming tutorial

Fig. 5. BackUP health tech tutorial

Fig. 6. Robot programming tutorial

Fig. 7. Hololens gesture tutorial

3.1 Learning Outcomes and Challenges

As argued in [6], the case demonstrated that the students were able to conduct a contextual analysis of user needs and apply these as well as theoretical knowledge to their video tutorial designs. Particularly theory on tacit and explicit knowledge was used to explain and reflect on different aspects of learning processes facilitated through visual aids and video tutorials. The students worked creatively with the design

and development of the tutorials, and feedback from users and co-students was incorporated into and improving the tutorials in the second iteration. However, the student evaluation questionnaire also revealed certain challenges, particularly related to developing a curriculum relevant to two very different study programs as well as to ensure the transferability of knowledge and skills from the course to future careers, which we will elaborate in the following.

3.2 Facilitating Engagement and Entrepreneurial Skills

In addition to the specific learning outcomes addressed in the course, the PBL principles (with regard to social, cognitive and content aspects) in our curriculum design (see *table 1*) were implemented to try to facilitate engagement and the development of entrepreneurial engineering skills.

From a *social learning approach*, the teamwork approach and self-directed learning facilitated engagement, and the students were particularly positive about sharing their work and reflections on the designated wiki-page. However some students found the workload of the project to somewhat withdraw from their general understanding of learning theories, particularly theory they did not directly apply to their project. The fact that they could choose cases related to their own technologies or start-up companies facilitated engagement and reflections with regard to entrepreneurial competences and future career, however students from Welfare Technology had difficulties connecting the development of video tutorials to their particular profession.

From a *cognitive learning approach*, the problem- and project-based learning facilitated engagement, however there was a rather big difference between the level to which students from Welfare Technology and Learning and Experience Technology found the course content and context relevant and to what extent they could draw from past experiences. Thus, the welfare technology context and its relation to learning might need to be explored and exemplified further in future curriculum designs.

From a *content learning approach*, the students were highly capable of applying theoretical knowledge to practice and discuss research methodologies in relation to their own profession, however the learning design could potentially benefit from increased attention to interdisciplinarity. For instance, since the students formed the groups themselves, they ended up dividing into groups according to their study program and thus did not fully utilize the potential for learning and knowledge sharing across disciplines. Group members with different backgrounds and diverse practices could perhaps also support the PBL principle of exemplarity, i.e. the transferability of knowledge, skills and competences to other contexts and domains as well as increase the visibility of knowledge and skills particular to the individual profession.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discussed the potentials and challenges of problem-based video tutorial design as an approach to facilitate learning, engagement and the development of entrepreneurial skills for engineering students in Welfare Technology and Learning

and Experience Technology. Future work includes further developing the curriculum in accordance with our PBL approach, particularly focusing on increasing interdisciplinarity and transferability of knowledge, skills and competences to related contexts and future careers within the Welfare, Learning and Experience Technology domains.

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